

ANALYSIS OF THE EFFECT OF PREFORM LAYUP AND GEOMETRY ON SHEET FORMING OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

This paper demonstrates the capability of a specially developed finite element model to predict the planar deformation and stress distribution in a laminate during forming. The model features the kinematic constraints of material incompressibility and fibre inextensibility. A mixed penalty finite element formulation is used, with independent discretization of the velocity and tension fields. The influence of sheet geometry, size and reinforcement directions on the stresses caused during central indentation of a large sheet is analysed. These stress distributions are used to predict the occurrence of the shear buckling and in-plane fibre wrinkling instabilities associated with this process.

1. INTRODUCTION

Sheet forming techniques for advanced composite materials are being actively investigated by many manufacturers, including such processes as diaphragm, matched metal, rubber-pad, roll and stretch forming. The development of a simulation capability to predict the stresses and deformations experienced by a composite sheet during processing would provide the fabricator with a greater understanding of the process forming limits.

Continuous fibre reinforced thermoplastics have performance and weight advantages over metals and rapid processing advantages over thermoset composites [1]. These attributes have already attracted considerable attention from industry. The development of fast, repeatable and reliable large scale manufacturing processes is necessary if fibre reinforced thermoplastics are to become viable alternatives to traditional fabrication materials. In order to achieve the necessary understanding of the important and unique features of composites processing, suitable mathematical analyses are being developed. The current research is focused on the development of finite element analysis process simulation methods for composite sheet forming. Such techniques are already widely used in the sheet metal forming industry, allowing prediction of the stresses and deformations experienced at each stage of the forming process.

2. SHEET FORMING TECHNIQUES

2.1 Diaphragm Forming

Diaphragm forming is a composites fabrication technique similar to vacuum forming of isotropic thermoplastic sheets[2,3]. The composite laminate, consisting of discrete unidirectional laminae, is held between two deformable sheets known as diaphragms, and formed against a tool by the application of a hydrostatic pressure. Only the diaphragms are clamped during forming, thus allowing free movement of the fibres. Forming takes place in a pressurized vessel known as an autoclave, at elevated temperatures. The feature of fibre reinforced thermoplastic materials which dominates their behaviour at forming temperatures is the very high anisotropy they exhibit. This is due to the fact that, during processing, the fibres remain solid, and retain their stiffness, while the matrix is softened to allow forming. This observation leads to the suggestion that the fibres may, in a mathematical analysis, be considered to be inextensible. Such a constraint severely restricts the

deformation patterns which may occur, and accounts for the unique behaviour of composite sheets during processing.

2.2 Forming Mechanisms

A full understanding of composite sheet forming requires an appreciation of the basic physical effects involved. At present, we are concerned with the single lamina case only. The principal deformation mechanism is identified as intraply shearing, where the fibres slide relative to each other (Figure 1(a)). This mechanism allows the composite sheet to take on complex shapes, despite the fact that the fibres are essentially inextensible. Resin flow relative to the fibres is not as significant with thermoplastic composites as it is with thermosets (Figure 1(b)). Pressure gradients along the material during forming lead to a squeeze flow mechanism which greatly influences part thickness (Figure 1(c)).

Figure 1. Forming Mechanisms (a) Intraply Shear (b) Resin Percolation (c) Squeeze Flow

2.3 Experimental Observations.

Of particular interest to experimental researchers is the occurrence of defects which will compromise the integrity of formed thermoplastic composite structures. These flaws include out-of-plane laminate buckling and in-plane fibre wrinkling. Forming small depressions in large reinforced

Figure 2. Cross Ply Hemisphere exhibiting Shear Buckling.

thermoplastic sheets causes a phenomenon known as shear buckling. In the case of forming a composite laminate into a hemispherical mould, buckles form at the rim of the mould, at 45° to the directions of reinforcement, as illustrated in Figure 2. This defect is irreversible after forming. An understanding of the causes and behaviour of this instability is considered necessary in order to manufacture shapes of double curvature with confidence.

An experimental study of these phenomena, using circular sheets, has been carried out at the University of Delaware and University College Galway [4]. An important conclusion of this study is that, for unidirectional, cross ply and quasi-isotropic sheets, symmetric wrinkles (out-of-plane) form at ± 45° to the directions of reinforcement. It was observed that increasing the outer diameter of the circular preform tended to increase the severity of buckling observed. It was further noted that the shear buckling instability is dependent on forming rate, indicating that stress levels in the composite are a controlling factor. Increasing diaphragm material stiffness is shown to alleviate the buckling phenomenon. An experiment is reported in which a quasi-isotropic sheet is formed into a hemispherical mould. Prior to the experiment, nickel coated tracer fibres had been embedded in the centre ply of the lay-up prior to forming. In-plane fibre buckling is seen to occur in the centre ply, and is most severe at the point where the fibres are tangent to the rim of the mould.

3. CONSTITUTIVE MODEL FOR COMPOSITE SHEET FORMING

3.1 Ideal Fibre Reinforced Newtonian Fluid

The constitutive model which will be employed describe the material behaviour observed in the processing of composite sheets is that of the Ideal Fibre Reinforced Newtonian Fluid. This model features the twin constraints of fibre inextensibility and material incompressibility[5]. These constraints lead to the appearance in the constitutive equations of two arbitrary stress terms, a hydrostatic pressure and a tension stress in the fibre direction. This model has recently been used to produce useful analytical solutions for problems associated with certain simple forming configurations[6].

For sheet forming problems, the assumption of plane stress in the 1-2 plane of the composite lamina is justified. The constitutive relationship for an Ideal Fibre Reinforced Newtonian Fluid then becomes :

$$\begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{11} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ \sigma_{12} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} D_{11}+D_{33} & D_{33} & D_{16} \\ D_{33} & D_{22} + D_{33} & D_{26} \\ D_{16} & D_{26} & D_{66} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} d_{11} \\ d_{22} \\ 2d_{12} \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} Tm^2 \\ Tn^2 \\ mnT \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

The terms of the viscous constitutive matrix are given as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} D_{11} &= 2\eta_T(1-2m^2) + 4\eta_L m^2 & D_{22} &= 2\eta_T(1-2n^2) + 4\eta_L n^2 \\ D_{33} &= 2\eta_T & D_{66} &= \eta_L \\ D_{16} &= D_{26} = 2(\eta_L - \eta_T)mn \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where :

η_L is the longitudinal shear viscosity. T is an arbitrary tension in the fibre direction.
 η_T is the transverse shear viscosity.

d is the infinitesimal rate of strain tensor:
$$d_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial v_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial v_j}{\partial x_i} \right)$$

where v is the velocity vector.

$m = \cos\theta$, $n = \sin\theta$ where θ is the angle the fibre makes with the 1 axis.

We note that the arbitrary hydrostatic pressure term does not appear in these equations. It can be obtained using the relation:

$$p = -D_{33} (d_{11} + d_{22}) \quad (3)$$

The constraint equations, for the case of 1-2 plane stress, become :

Incompressibility $\frac{\partial v_1}{\partial x_1} + \frac{\partial v_2}{\partial x_2} + \frac{\partial v_3}{\partial x_3} = 0$ (4)

Inextensibility $\cos^2\theta \frac{\partial v_1}{\partial x_1} + \cos\theta \sin\theta \left(\frac{\partial v_1}{\partial x_2} + \frac{\partial v_2}{\partial x_1} \right) + \sin^2\theta \frac{\partial v_2}{\partial x_2} = 0$ (5)

The constitutive equations describe the relationship between the stress state and the strain rate of a fluid, and the arbitrary tension is required to satisfy the equilibrium equations. The equations of motion are solved in conjunction with the constitutive equations and the kinematic constraint equations. The equilibrium equations for a fluid are written, in indicial notation, as :

$$\sigma_{ij,j} + b_i = 0 \text{ in } \Omega \text{ (i, j = 1, 2, 3)} \quad (6)$$

where Ω is the problem domain and b represents the body forces acting on the fluid.

The boundary traction equations are written as :

$$t_j = n_i \sigma_{ij} \text{ on } \Gamma_t \text{ (i, j = 1, 2, 3)} \quad (7)$$

where Γ_t is the problem boundary on which the tractions, t_j are prescribed and n_i are the components of the unit normal vector to the boundary.

3.2 Finite Element Formulation

Because of the complexity of typical sheet forming configurations, analytical approaches to process simulation will meet with limited success. Numerical simulations are clearly the appropriate direction for future research. However, finite element analysis programs based on standard anisotropic constitutive laws experience numerical problems similar to those associated with analysis of incompressible media, when they are used to model highly anisotropic materials[7]. The development of a finite element model for the Ideal Fibre Reinforced Newtonian Fluid requires special techniques (known as mixed penalty formulation), but computational difficulties are avoided. The procedure involves independent discretization of the velocity and tension fields, using a set of velocity shape functions N^v and a set of tension shape functions N^t . The formulation is based on that of the consistent penalty approach to problems of Stokes flow, and details of the derivation are published elsewhere [8,9]. The equation system reduces to :

$$\{ K + \alpha K^t (M)^{-1} (K^t)^T \} a^v = f \quad (8)$$

where :

$$K_{ij} = \int_{\Omega} (B_i^v)^T D B_j^v d\Omega \quad K_{ij}^t = \int_{\Omega} (B_i^v)^T a N_j^t d\Omega$$

$$f = - \int_{\Omega} (N_i^v)^T b d\Omega - \int_{\Gamma} (N_i^v)^T t d\Gamma \quad M_{ij}^t = \int_{\Omega} N_i^t N_j^t d\Omega$$

where α is the inextensibility penalty number, and standard finite element notation is used for matrices. The tension stress field may be recovered using the following relationship :

$$a^t = \alpha (M^t)^{-1} (K^t)^T a^v \quad (9)$$

4. FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

4.1 Planar Model for Forming of a Composite Hemisphere

The finite element models to be used in this investigation of the behaviour of the shear buckling instability must satisfy the requirements of the plane stress assumption. For this reason, the region of the composite sheet which is modeled is the flange region, which has not yet formed into the mould. These are suitable models because it is in this region of the sheet that the instabilities have been observed to occur. Also, several of the factors which are known to influence shear buckling may be incorporated into these models, leading to an enhanced understanding of their interaction with each other, i.e. sheet size, shape and fibre orientation. Three geometries are used in this paper (Figure 3), and the characteristic parameters of each are varied in order to assess their influence on the buckling phenomenon. Figure 3(a) represents a circular sheet, with fibres running in the Y-direction, and incorporates the associated symmetry boundary conditions. The inner circular region represents an Ideal Fibre Reinforced Newtonian Fluid, while the outer region is modeled as an isotropic viscous

fluid, representing the planar effect of the diaphragm stiffness on the forming situation. A uniform unit pressure is applied at the inner radius of the model, to simulate the hydrostatic pressure used to form the component. Figure 3 (b) and (c) are both used to model the forming of a square sheet, with fibres running at 45° and 0° to the sides of the square, respectively. The diaphragm is clamped at the outside diameter.

Figure 3 Analysis Models (a) Circular Sheet (+ 90°), (b) Square Sheet (+ 45°)
(c) Square Sheet (+ 90°)

4.2 Analysis Details and Results for Circular Sheets.

The finite element formulation described previously is incorporated in the finite element program FEFORM. The planar models described in the previous section are meshed using these elements (Figure 4). A parameter study, involving the process variables which may be adjusted by the manufacturer, is required. The issue of primary concern in this paper is the effect of sheet shape and reinforcement direction on the stresses caused during forming. A previous publication has detailed the effect of varying diaphragm stiffness, sheet diameter, indentation size and composite shear viscosities on forming with a circular, unidirectional sheet[10].

For a circular composite sheet, a peak shear stress is predicted at the inner radius of the model at roughly 45° to the fibre direction, the shear buckling location. Axial, shear and transverse stresses at the inner radius are shown in Figure 5. The effect of increasing the diaphragm stiffness is to reduce the peak shear stress caused, particularly at smaller ratios of outer diameter to inner diameter (Figure 6). A compressive axial stress singularity is predicted at the point where the fibres are tangent to the mould rim, where in-plane fibre buckling has been experimentally observed. The study reveals that this may be alleviated by using stiffer diaphragms, for an 8 inch diameter sheet. Figure 7 shows that for higher diaphragm viscosities, an increase in composite sheet diameter will bring about a decrease in the magnitude of the compressive axial stresses at this point, hence alleviating in-plane buckling. For lower values of diaphragm viscosity, the pattern changes, with medium size sheets being most sensitive to in-plane buckling. In general, the advantage of an increased diaphragm viscosity is confirmed, for all sheet sizes. It is noted that the stresses which cause in-plane fibre buckling and those which cause shear buckling (out-of-plane) respond differently to altering the sheet size. A compromise between the two effects will be necessary to ensure good part quality.

4.3 Effect of Sheet Size, Shape and Fibre Orientation

The shear stress distributions predicted for both of the square unidirectional sheets (0° and 45°) are similar to those previously reported. The peak values are at the inner radius of the models, at approximately 45° to the directions of reinforcement. A study of the effect of sheet size is shown in Figure 8, using the maximum fibre length as the characteristic length. The similarity of the results for the different geometries suggests that this parameter controls shear buckling. In terms of shear buckling, it is always advantageous to minimize the size of the sheet used.

4.4 Effect of Sheet Shape on Cross Ply and Quasi-isotropic Sheets

In real structural components, there will usually be more than one direction of reinforcement. In order to treat cases involving several fibre orientations, the assumption is made that each of the plies deforms independently of the others in forming. The degree of interaction between plies is assumed to be negligible. Stress analysis is carried out for each ply independently. The laminate stress is then calculated by an averaging procedure, since the whole laminate must buckle. The effect of increasing the number of reinforcement directions on the tangential stresses for a circular sheet (7 inch diameter), is shown in Figure 9. The values presented here are the stresses calculated at the inner radius of the model, representing the rim of the mould, where instabilities occur. The distribution for the

unidirectional case incorporates the compressive axial stress at the point where the fibre directions are tangential to the inner radius, which was described earlier. In general, the level of tangential stress at the rim of the mould is reduced for the cross ply case, although the value at 45° is the same, due to the averaging procedure. The quasi-isotropic sheet shows peak values of compressive tangential stress at $\pm 45^\circ$ to the reinforcement directions. As the number of reinforcement directions increases, the solution approaches that of an isotropic material, which is a uniform unit tangential stress.

Using the same procedure as above, the tangential stress results for a (0/90) cross ply square and a ($\pm 45^\circ$) cross ply square are calculated. Figure 10 shows a comparison of the three cross ply stress distributions predicted. At 45° , the difference between the results is small, but at 0° and 90° , the tangential stress for the ($\pm 45^\circ$) laminate is significantly less than for the other two arrangements. This is due to a reduction in the magnitude of the compressive tangential stress for this configuration of sheet. A reduction in in-plane fibre buckling at these locations is therefore predicted. We now turn our attention to quasi-isotropic sheets (with fibres in the $+45^\circ$, -45° , 0° and 90° directions). Figure 11 shows a comparison between the tangential stresses predicted for a square and circular quasi-isotropic sheet. The reduced compressive tangential stress for the ($\pm 45^\circ$) sheet now has an effect at the 45° buckling site, due to the contribution of the -45° ply. This leads to a reduced compressive tangential stress at this point, which reduces the likelihood of buckling. Therefore a square quasi-isotropic sheet should be less susceptible to buckling at the 45° point than a circular sheet.

5 CONCLUSIONS

A method has been presented for predicting the stress distributions experienced in diaphragm forming a composite hemisphere from sheets with different shapes, sizes and directions of reinforcement. The maximum shear stress predicted for each geometry increases with sheet size. The axial stresses responsible for fibre buckling decrease as the sheet diameter increases, and all stresses in the sheet are reduced by using stiffer diaphragms.

The effect of additional directions of reinforcement is explored. For cross ply sheets, sheet geometry does not have a significant effect on shear buckling, but a ($\pm 45^\circ$) square offers an advantage over the other configurations in terms of in-plane fibre buckling. As the number of reinforcement directions increases, the solution approaches that of an isotropic material, as would be expected. In quasi-isotropic sheets, the phenomena which cause the instabilities interact. In the case of a square quasi-isotropic sheet, a reduced compressive axial stress in the -45° ply alleviates the shear buckling problem, as well as possible fibre buckling. For this reason, a square quasi-isotropic sheet is less prone to buckling at 45° than a circular one.

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Figure 4. Typical Mesh used in Finite Element Analysis Procedure.

Figure 5. Axial, Shear and Transverse Stresses for a Unidirectional Circular Sheet.

Figure 6. Effect of Sheet Diameter Ratio and Diaphragm Viscosity on Shear Stress

Figure 7. Effect of Sheet Diameter and Diaphragm Viscosity on Axial Stresses.

Figure 8. Effect of Sheet Shape and Size on Peak Shear Stress.

Figure 9. Effect of Additional Directions of Reinforcement on Tangential Stresses.

Figure 10. Comparison of Tangential Stresses for Different Cross Ply Laminates

Figure 11. Comparison of Tangential Stresses for Different Quasi-isotropic Sheets.